

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES WITH A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ANNOTATION: Involvement of quality system certification experts, registered certification staff and technical experts in the work on quality management system certification. Based on the customer's request to determine the scope of the quality management system and the audit results, the certification office determines the scope of the quality management system certification.

KEY WORDS: product, standard, metrology, resources, certification, , quality, equipment, calibration, international standards, quality management system, safety.

As a result of the certification of the quality management system, the level of compliance of the inspected enterprise and organization with the requirements of ISO 9001 and the effectiveness of the quality management system is determined. Certification of students, quality management system certification is carried out by ISO/IEC62, Uz DSt ISO19011 and quality system certification standard, quality system certification agencies accredited in the National Certification System. Certification is carried out in documented enterprises that have a quality management system and have been officially implemented. Quality management system certification experts, registered certification staff and, if necessary, technical experts are involved in the work on quality management system certification. The customer determines the field of application of the quality management system, and

based on the application and audit results, the certification office determines the field of certification of the quality management system. The field of application of the quality management system as audit objects in the certification of the quality management system, conformity of product quality to consumer requirements and mandatory requirements for this product, documentation in the quality management system, the complete and clear presence of the requirements of ISO 9001, the working status of the processes of the quality management system, system documentation. It is important to ensure the fulfillment of requirements and the effectiveness of the Quality Management System [1].

The main tasks in the certification of the quality management system are the organization of certification work, the conclusion of a contract for the certification of the quality management system, the certification office evaluates the information and labor costs used in the recommendations for standardization in the certification. The commission will consist of one or several experts. When determining the composition and participants of the commission, it is necessary to take into account the purpose, scope and criteria of the audit, the duration of the audit, the types of economic activity of the organization, the different location of the audited organization with the production area, the number of employees of the audited organization, the labor cost during the audit, the commission for the purpose of the audit in the future. It is necessary to determine the need to ensure the competence, the requirements of legal and normative legal acts, technical regulations adopted for conducting the assessment, ensuring the independence of the commission members from the organization to be certified, the possibilities of effective interaction between the audited organization and the commission members, and the language of the audit.

In order to confirm the multi-faceted competence of the commission, it is necessary to identify the knowledge and skills for the purpose of the future audit, to select the members of the commission taking into account the special knowledge in

the specification of production processes, the audit method and procedure, and the multi-faceted knowledge level criteria. If the experts in the commission do not have the skills and necessary knowledge on specific types of economic activity, then the commission may add technical experts to the commission [2].

In the analysis of the quality management system documents, the audited organization determines the conformity of the system documents with the requirements of ISO 9001. If necessary, according to the agreement of the certification office with the audited organization, the audited organization may send its representatives for an on-site introduction to the Quality Management System or on a business trip to resolve unclear issues. Additional agreements or additional contract conditions are agreed upon with the customer of such business trips. Simultaneously with the analysis of the received documents, the commission organizes the collection and analysis of additional evidence about the organization's product, which has been accepted for certification of the Quality Management System. Sources of information Consumers, government inspection and control agencies, consumer groups, workmanship guarantees, trade organizations and others can serve as sources of information. The analysis is concluded with the official formalization of the report on the initial inspection of the Quality Management System documents, in which the identified and found deficiencies are stated in the conclusion whether it is possible or not to conduct an audit of the Quality Management System "on-site".

Preparation for the "on-site audit" preliminary cross-activity with the audited organization is carried out for the following purposes: it is necessary to determine the ways of exchanging information with the audited organization, to approve documents in accordance with the agreed procedure, to agree on the procedure for ensuring the safety of the activities of experts in the production areas, to determine the reception of representatives of the audited organization, participants in the audit [3].

In the development of the audit plan, the purpose of the audit, the basis for the audit, the schedule and duration of the audit, the commission's general acquaintance with the organization and the conclusion of the first and last meeting with the head of the audited organization, the identification of the audit field and the structural units included in the quality management system of the audited organization, the date of the audit in the structural structure and the audit where it will be held, the elements of the quality management system being audited (clauses of ISO 9001 of ISO 9001), the obligations to the members of the audit plan, the identification of the representatives of the audited organization, and the confidentiality requirements.

Preparation of working documents. Experts prepare working documents under the guidance of the chairman of the commission. Sample forms developed by the certification office can be used to prepare for the audit. In the working documents, the list of selective control plans and inspection questions, registration and review of the non-conformity form, the Certification Office must ensure that all audit records and documents are kept until the end of the audit [4].

Initial meeting. The initial meeting is held under the leadership of the commission chairman with the participation of commission members, management and leading specialists of the audited organization. The purpose of the meeting is to confirm the possibility of using the audit plan, to briefly cover the use of audit procedures and methods, to officially establish the procedure for the interaction of the commission members and employees of the audited organization, and to discuss the issues that arise. During the meeting, the participants will be introduced to the work assigned to them by the commission during the audit, the schedule of audit work will be announced, the time and date of the last meeting, other activities related to the audit, and interim meetings will be introduced to the management of the audit commission and the audited organization, a brief introduction to the audit procedure and method, audit to provide information in advance to the organization that the evaluation results are not subject to probability description, to inform the

organization about the audit work, to notify the audited organization of information about the conduct of the audit, to confirm the commission's compliance with confidentiality requirements, to ensure the safety and health requirements for the members of the commission provide advance information about the decision taken on the results of approval and certification and the rules of the compliance procedure, introduce the procedure for drawing up an act, inform about the conditions under which the audit can be suspended providing information, in case of inconsistency in the act, it is considered important to inform the audited organization in advance about issues in the further activities of the certification office.

Interviews with the employees of the investigated organization, private observation of the workplace, working conditions and employee activities by an expert, feedback from consumers, Quality Management System documents, quality policy and goals, quality manual, quality plan, organization standards as data sources. (documented procedures), technological regulations (technological processes), statutes, guidelines and external regulatory and technical documents, contracts and other such documents, consisting of information about the processes of the Quality Management System (records), internal audit acts (report), by the management documents such as analysis reports, product test reports, meeting decisions on quality problems, information on the results of process and product measurement and monitoring, work logs, filled-in records, forms and scales, etc., quality management system performance analysis ili data review, supplier rating and evaluation results. Information from the above-mentioned sources must be objective, truthful and verified. Classification and registration of conclusions. During the audit of the quality management system, all deviations of the audit objects from the requirements of ISO 9001 are eliminated, and the documents of the organization's quality management system are carefully reviewed and classified, and it is agreed with the commission that the audit object is not related to the level of inconsistency. The conclusions made in the audit are classified by the audited

organization with the purpose of corrective actions (to eliminate the cause of non-conformity), the correctness of the sequence of identified non-conformities, the decision taken by the certification office, the cancellation or termination of the certificate activity, and the expansion of the certification area. A type of non-unilateral reversible multi-valued non-conformity (related to one of the elements of the Quality Management System) requires justification to be converted to a significant non-conformity. The chairman of the commission makes the final decision on the concept of non-compliance criteria. Inconsistencies and deficiencies will be eliminated in the established forms. No corrections are allowed on the form. Recorded inconsistencies and deficiencies are formally presented to the management of the organization under investigation.

Activities carried out with non-conformity and notification (warning), the commission will officially provide the head of the audited organization with registered non-conformities and information, the opportunity for the organization to review and discuss it during the registration of non-conformity and notification (warning), if the organization eliminates the non-conformity and informs (warning), if the commission provides evidence during the course of work, the commission will accept such inconsistency or information as absent if these inconsistencies or notifications (warnings) are issued in accordance with the registration form. The number of non-conformities and notifications (warnings) is given in the document and taken into account in the decision to issue (not to issue) a certificate of conformity. puts his signature. If it is difficult for the audited organization to plan corrective actions during the certification audit, the certification office provides an additional week (until the day of the final meeting) to complete the specified works. The certification body will report its objections to the plan to the audited organization, after which it will revise the plan this week. The period of implementation of the planned corrective actions should not deviate from the plan and should not be confused, 12 weeks (from the date of the final meeting) when one

or more significant non-conformities are found, and 5 weeks (from the date of the final meeting) when only minor non-conformities and notifications (warnings) are found [5].

The chairman of the commission takes responsibility for the composition and preparation of the report on the audit results. Before holding the meeting, the audit observation (summary) is analyzed, and optional various data are collected during the audit and its compliance with the objectives is seen, the detected inconsistencies and observations are analyzed, the audit object is taken into account in the description of the sample, and the document on the audit results is drawn up, the organization issues a certificate of conformity of the Quality Management System prepares a recommendation to the certification body for a decision on (non-grant), discusses next activities (for example, conducting an inspection). The document contains identification of the certification office, identification of the customer-organization, purpose and scope of the audit, basis for conducting the audit, time and place of conducting the audit, identification of technical experts along with the chairman of the committee on certification and members of the commission, identification of the normative basis of the audit, audit results, commission conclusion, it is important to indicate the address in the document.

Quality management system certification cannot be completed without checking all planned corrective actions and the results of their implementation. The commission may consider the work completed if all tasks have been completed, the audit plan has been reviewed, the report on the audit results has been completed and signed by the parties, and the commission has submitted a report and plan on the implementation of corrective actions. Documents related to the audit will be stored or canceled in accordance with the applicable legislation, regulations and contracts, as well as documents of the certification office. Quality management system certification documents are stored in the certification office based on the rules established in accordance with the documents of the certification office. The head

of the certification office and the commission should not disclose to other voluntary parties the content of the report on the results of the audit, other information and documents obtained during the audit, without agreement with the audited organization (customer) [6].

The quality management system is in accordance with the established requirements and the criteria for making a decision about non-conformity and issuing/not issuing a certificate are the absence of non-conformities in the inspected organization or corrective actions within the agreed period, and the certification body's implementation/non-implementation of the results of their corrective actions and acceptance/non-acceptance. The head of the certification office makes a decision on issuing or canceling the certificate of conformity of the quality management system based on the results of the corrective actions according to the plan and the report. The decision should be made by the person who did not accept to participate in the audit. The certification body is scheduled to monitor the implementation of corrective actions on established non-conformities after receiving a written report from the audited organization on the elimination of non-conformities. Implementation of corrective actions on significant non-conformities is monitored by a mandatory visit of the expert(s) of the certification office to the audited organization. In the control of the implementation of corrective actions for minor non-conformities, it is allowed to consider the official report of the audited organization, if the content of the corrective actions does not require a mandatory "on-site" inspection. During the audit, the expert verifies the effectiveness of the corrective actions actually performed and in order to control the implementation of the corrective actions. If corrective actions on non-conformities are not satisfied according to objective evidence, the organization's Quality Management System assessment and audit result will be negatively affected, and the certification office will notify the cancellation of the certificate.

With the positive decision of the certification office, the Quality Management System is issued in the form of a certificate of conformity. At the certification office, a list number is assigned to the certificate, and then the certificate is registered in the registry of the certification office. There may also be a certificate attachment. The head of the certification office makes a decision on formalizing the application for the certificate. The head of the certification office or his deputy and the chairman of the commission sign the conducted audit and certificate. The seal of the certification office is placed on the certificate. The technical center gives the account number of the certificate to the quality system registry at the request of the certification office. The account number is placed at the bottom of the certificate frame. The account number is composed of a five-digit register list showing the serial number of the certificate. After the quality management system conformity certificate is issued, the certification office submits a copy of the certificate to the technical center of the quality system registry for official publication of the information. [7].

Inspection control can be scheduled and unscheduled. Planned inspection control is carried out at least once a year during the validity period of the certificate. Scheduled inspection control is conducted during the validity period of the certificate at intervals of 6, 10 and other months. Audit objects are defined in scheduled inspection control. Scheduled inspection should not be less than 1/2 elements of the quality management system in addition to the total inspection volume. In each inspection, the following set of mandatory elements are checked, document requirements, quality goals, management analysis, resource management, customer satisfaction, internal audits (inspection), improvement, certification and use of conformity marks. If during unscheduled inspection, the certification office receives information about serious violations from the certified Quality Management System, and at the same time information about consumer complaints about the quality of products produced by the certificate holder, the organization's

organizational structure, technology, production conditions, staff and personnel composition, and similar changes occur. unplanned inspection is determined by the reasons for audit objects in control, the necessity of inspection control. After the certification office receives advance payments from the inspection agreement, the head of the certification office appoints the chairman of the inspection control commission and the inspection control commission is formed [8].

In accordance with the requirements of the governing documents (inspection control), the participants of the commission members are determined based on the volume of audit work, the difficulty of checking objects and their number. The chairman of the commission draws up a plan for inspection control of the certified Quality Management System. Inspection results, conclusions and recommendations are formalized by the commission in the form of a document and submitted to the certification office.

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